

CONVERSION IN MODERN ENGLISH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6245759>

Gulamjanova Kamila

*National University of The Republik of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek*

S.A.Hashimova

Supervisor: DSc, assos.prof.

Abstract: *Following article covers information about word formation and one of its type conversion, its origin meaning and linguistic meaning.*

Key words: *word formation, affixation, compounding, conversion, contraction, word fusion, lexicography, lexical category.*

Language is a big science where people can be lost in it like in an enormous forest. It has many branches that should be investigated and so many divisions. Approaching the language according to its grammatical sections also one of the most important matter, that demands deeply analysis. From this approaches the word building also has its own immense impact not only on grammar section, but also on its vocabulary side. As the language becomes richer and alive according to the number used words in it and the meaning. Language enriches its vocabulary section by the several types of word forming. The emergence of new words in the language occurs in various ways: 1) by borrowing from other languages; 2) with the help of word formation (affixation, compounding, conversion, contraction, word fusion, etc.); 3) as a result of the emergence of new meanings of words already existing in the language. Based on this, following article will cover the information about “conversion”, one of the types of word forming.

Major aim of this article is to provide fully definition to the word conversion and at the same time to analyze the word forming structure itself, how it works and how many are there types of word formation.

The object of this work is the phenomenon of conversion in English. The subject of this work is the study of the main features of the converses. For observing and learning this section closely helped many literatures and web sites as: Raymond Hickey. “The Neat Dictionary of Linguistics”, Gregory Trauth and Kerstin Kazzazi Routledge “Dictionary of Language and”, Hojiyev A. “O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati”, <https://www.merriam->

webster.com/dictionary, <https://dictionary.cambridge.org>, Titik Sudartinah. On Conversion In English October 2016. these literature closely helped out to work on this article and gave useful information.

As words are becoming base of language its enlarging closely connected with lexicography and grammar. In grammar section we have several types of word forming, they are: affixation, compounding, conversion, contraction, word fusion. From this form conversion always became disputable among linguists and it is thought as one of the confusing part of the word building while it is the essential one. Initially there stated some dictionary and literature facts about the word itself conversion what is it and what does it mean? So let's analyze it deeper: conversion is the use of an item of one class in another without any formal change, e.g. to breakfast from breakfast. Conversion is a common feature of analytical languages such as English¹. Moreover, conversion can be classified as follows:

1 Relation of semantic opposition that denotes the polarity between two-place predicates and is defined as an equivalence relation: If Philip is older than Caroline, then Caroline is younger than Philip (and vice versa). Such converse expressions usually take the form of polar adjectives, of verbs that describe relations of exchanging (give: receive, buy: sell, and the like) and of kinship terms (father: son, etc.).

2 Process of word formation brought about by a change in lexical category of a base (to drive>a drive) and also of compound stems (to sandpaper), but also exceptionally those with a prefix or suffix. In contemporary English, denominal verbs are particularly productive (productivity): (to) bicycle, (to) stamp; similarly, deverbal nouns: hit, buy, and deadjectival verbs: to tidy. Instead of a process of transferring one stem category into the other, Marchand (1960) understands conversion as derivation with the aid of a zero morpheme.²

The term conversion is not used only in English, this term can be seen in any language for example there can be stated short information from the Russian dictionary: Adverbialization is one type of semantic in grammar section of word forming: the transition from one part of speech to another one, that is conversion. Conversion is word formation of words by changing the composition of the word form which is known as paradigm. By the following way of word formation the word not only changes its form as a

¹ Raymond Hickey. *The Neat Dictionary of Linguistics*. - P16.

² Gregory Trauth and Kerstin Kazzazi. *Routledge Dictionary of Language and Linguistics*. Taylor & Francis e-Library, 2006. - P.255

part of speech, but also it changes its grammatical features, lexical meaning also.

Conversion from Latin means converting, changing. Main features are semantic grammatical word formation by changing its speech. The main types of conversion are: substantiation, adjectivation and adverbialization, i.e. the formation of nouns, adjectives and adverbs based on the forms of other parts of speech.³

From the above stated it can be overseen that adverbialization is one type of word forming by the feature of semantic grammar, that is from one part of speech to another one, simply saying conversion. Conversion term is used to the type of word forming that changes form of the word, its paradigm. Overcoming this change the word not only changes part of the speech (especially adverb), but also it changes grammatical and lexical meaning also.

Conversion from Latin means change, main type of word forming semantic grammatically by changing its form. By changing form they also change lexical and grammatical function as well. Main types of conversion are noun forming verb forming and adverb forming from the other types of the speech.

Here are some more definitions from Uzbek resources also: “Konversiya – aylantirish o'zgartirish, almashtirish” “Conversion – noun, con·ver·sion | \ kən-'vər-zhən , -shən \”⁴.

While some online resources can cover short and clear definition of conversion, they are:

1: the act of converting: the process of being converted

2: an experience associated with the definite and decisive adoption of a religion

3 a: the operation of finding a converse in logic or mathematics

b: reduction of a mathematical expression by clearing of fractions

4: a successful attempt for a point or points especially after a touchdown or for a first down a 2-point conversion a third-down conversion

5: something converted from one use to another”⁵

Above mentioned definitions were given in dictionaries that covers the term conversation and how to make conversation while the terminology dictionaries give some linguistic approach with the forms of conversion that

³ Жеребило Татьяна Васильевна. СЛОВАРЬ ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ. Назрань Издательство ООО «Пилигрим», 2010. - С.161.

⁴ Hojiyev A. va boshqalar O'zbek tili izohli ug'ati. - Toshkent, 2008. – B. 398.

⁵ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary>

changes its form to the noun, verb, adjective and adverb. Conversion involves the change of a word from one word class to another. For example, the verbs to email and to microwave are formed from the nouns email and microwave: Can you text her? (verb from noun text, meaning to send a text-message). They are always jetting somewhere. (verb from noun jet). If you're not careful, some downloads can damage your computer. (noun from verb download). OK, so the meeting's on Tuesday. That's a definite. (noun from adjective). It's a very big if and I'm not at all sure we can afford it. (noun from conjunction, meaning 'it's not at all certain'). All companies have their ups and downs. (nouns from prepositions). We also use conversion when we change a proper noun into a common noun: Has anybody seen my Dickens? (copy of a book by Dickens)⁶

Conversion as one of the main ways of forming words in modern English is very productive. The term "conversion", which many linguists consider inappropriate, refers to numerous cases of phonetic coincidence of word forms, mainly in the so-called initial forms, of two words belonging to different parts of speech. Conversion can be illustrated by the following examples: work - to work; love - to love, etc.

Obviously, in the case of a noun and a verb, not only the initial forms (ie, the infinitive and the nominative singular) are phonetically identical, but also some others. However, it should be remembered that although the importance of inflections has significantly decreased in the English language over the past eight or nine years, there is a certain difference between the various parts of speech at the morphological level, mainly between the noun and the verb. But in a case like water - to water at the level of word formation it is clear that the verb is formed from a noun without any morphological changes. But looking deeper, the inevitable conclusion is that the two words have a different paradigm. Thus, it is the paradigm that is used for word formation. Therefore, we can define conversion as a way of forming new words by changing their paradigm. There is no doubt that the reason for the widespread use of conversion in modern English is the absence of morphological elements that serve as indicators of classes or forms that mark those parts of speech to which the given word belongs. The last process of English word-formation is called conversion. It refers to a change in the function of a word, for example when a noun comes to be used as a verb without any reduction or addition of affixes. Other labels for this process are category change and functional shift. Conversion mainly occurs on nouns and verbs. However, it is possible that other word-classes

⁶ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org>

also undergo it. Some examples of words formed by conversion are guess (verb to noun), experience (noun to verb), good (adjective to noun). The later parts of the paper discuss conversion especially on the concepts related to it, its characteristics and process, and the meanings of words formed through conversion especially that involves nouns, verbs, and adjectives. There are many examples showing the existence of conversion. However, "the process of conversion is not as simple as it seems. This process is easy to be recognized since both words involved (the original and derivative) are identical in spelling. Besides die change in the function, the derived words formed through conversion sometimes also have different meanings from those of the original. As word building has immense impact on the vocabulary of the language, this field still being observed carefully and in detail. Following this the observation of Titik Sudartinah on work "On Conversion In English" the term conversion was observed and analyzed deeply. He mentioned this form of word building as a last stage of word formation.

To recapitulate briefly this article covered small section of word forming in grammar section of linguistics while it demanded deep research and fully understanding of the matter. At the beginning of the article can be seen the introduction of the term conversion what it is and how we can understand this term. From the introduction it became clear that conversion is a type of word forming and it has immense impact on the vocabulary of the language.

The article is followed by the aim of this work and clearly defined the objects and subjects of this work. And in this section was stated some resources that helped to work over the research.

And from the main part we understood that different researches and linguists gave different opinion on conversion while it still remained as one of the crucial issue of the grammar section. Owing to it helps to remain the language alive. If the language does not enriches it is vocabulary, its use can be limited. Following these features it can be clear that conversion also important and interesting field that helps to enlarge the vocabulary. Moreover, conversion covers its division also that changes its form and grammar structure also.

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